

Incorporating economic valuation into sustainable agriculture system

Akhmad Fauzi

Bogor Agricultural University

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Prof. Akhmad Fauzi, Ph.D
Faculty of Economics and Management
Bogor Agricultural University

Development Paradox

This is a clear example of lacking synergy between economic aspects and agriculture sustainability

How the synergy of economic and sustainable agriculture work?

The role of natural capital in national wellbeing

Constanza et al, 2014

Economic Valuation for Food and Agriculture

- Economic valuation is a pivotal part for food and agriculture by ensuring food availability through ecosystem services (water provision, quality and soil fertility)

Economic Valuation of Agriculture support 8 goals of SDGs

Agriculture Valuation reduces poverty through ecosystem services

Deliver through localeconomic
development

- Increase productivity through ecosystem service
- Combined with ecotourism
- Small and medium enterprises

Reduce poverty

Valuation reduces hunger (SDG no 2)

Economic value of agriculture to well being

Valuasi dalam Proyek Pertanian

Economic Value of Agricultural Services

Jasa Lingkungan Pertanian	Nilai
Pengaturan hama	US\$ 70 -260 /ha/tahun
Nilai rekreasi (perikanan)	3 -9% darinilai lahan
Rekreasi (Hunting)	\$ 1.9- US\$ 2.2/trip/tahun
Pengaturan banjir	2 -4 % nilai lahan pertanian
Water quality regulation	US\$ 40 -67 /ha/tahun

Other economic values

Table 1 Economic value of ecosystem services on arable farming lands in Canterbury, New Zealand (Source: Sandhu et al., 2008).

Ecosystem service	Economic value ^a	
	Organic farming	Conventional farming
Biological control of pests	50 (0-100)	0 (0-0)
Mineralisation of plant nutrients	260 (26-425)	142 (30-349)
Soil formation	6 (0.7-11)	5 (2-9)
Food	3,990 (1,150-18,900)	3,220 (840-14,000)
Raw materials	22 (0-224)	38 (0-298)
Carbon accumulation	22 (0-210)	20 (0-210)
Nitrogen fixation	40 (0-92)	43 (0-92)
Soil fertility	68 (53-82)	66 (54-73)
Hydrological flow	107 (-111-190)	54 (-118-194)
Pollination	62 (0-438)	64 (0-455)
Shelterbelts	880 (0-472)	200 (0-617)
Total	4,600 (1,607-19,412)	3,680 (1,263-14,570)

^a Means of calculated values in US\$/ha/yr, range of mean estimates in parentheses.

Nilai ekonomi total lahan basah secara global mencapai US\$ 14,9 triliun (Constanza et al, 2014)

Pemerintah kota New York membeli lahan basah sebesar US\$ 1,5 milyar untuk menghindari kerugian banjir sebesar US\$ 3 - 8 milyar (www.panda.org)

Example from West Java

Economic value of Rice Field in West Java

Size area 936.525 Ha
 Use Value Rp 39 trilyun

Fungsi Non -use	Nilai (Rp/Ha)
Pest contril	1, 95 juta
Aesthetic	273 ribu
Mineralisation	1,85 juta
Soil Fertility	858 ribu
Nitrogen Fixation	559 ribu
Carbon Accumulation	260 ribu
Water Quality	695 ribu
Bee polination	832 ribu
Shelterbelts	2,6 juta

Smiley Curve: Value capture of Agriculture Products

Concluding Remarks

- Synergi of economic and agriculture through economic valuation plays crucial role to ensure agriculture
- Economic valuation provides a correct signal to public policy on the "total value" of agriculture as a sustainable system encompassing economic, social and environmental dimensions.
- Economic valuation could avoid undervaluation of agriculture ecosystem which lead to massive land conversions and degradation
- Effective synergy could only be possible with support from policy makers and political will